
ELENE's YouTube Stats and Analytics

Elders learning English for Europe
2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10511017

Czestochowa, 2024

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Introduction

The screenshot shows the YouTube channel for 'Elene'. The channel name is 'Elene' with the handle '@Project_elene', 123 subscribers, and 81 videos. The bio states: 'Project ELENE: This partnership is formed by organizations from Poland, Slovenia, Spain, ...'. There are buttons for 'Customise channel' and 'Manage videos'. The navigation menu includes Home, Videos, Shorts, Playlists, and Community. Under 'Created playlists', there are eight playlists: 'Project dissemination' (1 video), 'App' (7 videos), 'Situation stories' (1 video), 'Short films' (10 videos), 'Vocabulary' (30 videos), 'Questions & Answers' (2 videos), 'Conversation practice' (32 videos), and 'ELENE meeting' (6 videos).

In the digital age, where learning transcends traditional classrooms, the Elene YouTube channel stands out as of innovative language education. With a growing following of 123 subscribers and a rich library of 81 videos, Elene is helpful for students and educators seeking a multifaceted approach to language acquisition. The channel's content is thoughtfully segmented into 8 playlists, each serving an aspect of language learning, from app tutorials to situational dialogues.

The **App Tutorial Playlist** is a cornerstone of the channel, offering multilingual guides for the Elene application. It's an invaluable resource for users to navigate the app's features across languages such as English, Spanish, Polish, Portuguese, Turkish, and Slovenian. Furthermore, the inclusion of a short film demonstrates the app in action, providing a silent but potent narrative on its utility.

Situation Stories Playlist: Tailored to augment lessons on unexpected situations, our 'Situation Stories' playlist present realistic scenarios, such as a traffic incident. This video serve as a valuable tool for practical learning and comprehension.

Short Films Playlist: Our short films are a blend of application demonstrations, project dissemination meetings, and interactive quizzes. These films are not only informative, but also serve as a creative medium to engage learners in the educational process.

The Vocabulary Playlist is an extensive compilation of 30 videos, each equipped with visual aids and clear narration, targeting a broad spectrum of topics sourced from the Elene textbook. This visual and auditory approach to vocabulary building is particularly suited to cater to diverse learning styles, making language acquisition more accessible.

For learners keen on mastering conversational English, the **Questions & Answers Playlist** offers a real-world application of textbook dialogues. Videos such as "Learn English with me | English Conversation Practice | ELENE Project" provide viewers with the opportunity to practice and enhance their communicative competencies.

The channel's **Conversation Practice Playlist** features 32 videos that employ artificial intelligence to create situational dialogues, offering a unique interactive learning experience. This series enables viewers to practice conversations by reading the blue subtitles and responding to the red, thereby simulating a natural dialogue exchange.

Lastly, the **ELENE Meeting Playlist** gives viewers an inside look at the collaborative efforts behind the ELENE project, highlighting the collective endeavours that contribute to the channel's educational outreach.

In conclusion, the Elene YouTube channel is a digital platform for English language learning. With its diverse content and commitment to educational innovation, Elene is not just a channel, but a digital classroom that extends learning opportunities to a global audience.

Channel Statistics

(MOST POPULAR VIDEOS)

The Elene YouTube channel emerges as a vanguard of interactive language learning. With a total of 6,207 views and 69.8 hours of watch time, this burgeoning channel has captivated an audience of 123 subscribers, generating 105,332 impressions with a notable click-through rate of 3.0%. This is a testament to the channel's engaging content and its effectiveness in capturing the interest of learners.

Among its varied educational offerings, the video "Learn English with me | Asking for directions | ELENE Project" stands out as the most popular, clocking in at 1 minute and 55 seconds. It has amassed 259 views, accounting for 4.2% of the channel's total views, and a watch time of 3.1 hours, which is 4.5% of the total watch time of the Elene channel. This particular tutorial has not only enriched viewers with knowledge but also contributed significantly to the channel's growth by drawing in 11 new subscribers, making up 8.9% of the total subscriber base. With 7,332 impressions and a click-through rate of 2.7%, it resonates with the audience's need for concise and practical language instruction.

In the realm of bite-sized learning, the short film "Test your English with us! #languagelearning #adult #elene #eleneproject #english #englishgrammar," with a duration of 51 seconds. It garnered 256 views, which represents 4.1% of the channel's total viewership. The film's brevity did not deter viewers from engaging deeply, as evidenced by its watch time of 1.2 hours, or 1.7% of the channel's total watch time. This engagement is particularly impressive given the short duration of the video. With 274 impressions and a click-through rate of 2.9%, it highlights the channel's adeptness at crafting content that sparks curiosity and encourages viewers to delve into the nuances of the English language.

Channel Statistics

(SUBSCRIPTIONS AND VIEWERSHIP)

The Elene YouTube channel the overall viewership stands at 6,207 views, with an average view duration of 40 seconds, and viewers have watched an average of 42.1% of each video. This indicates that while the content is capturing attention, there may be opportunities to optimize it to increase viewer retention throughout the entirety of each video.

An intriguing aspect of Elene's viewership is the distinction between subscribed and non-subscribed viewers.

Non-subscribed viewers, who constitute a majority of the views at 3,690, have a slightly lower engagement rate, with an average view duration of 37 seconds and 39.8% of each video watched, culminating in 38.7 hours of watch time. This group's metrics suggest that while the channel is successful in attracting a broader audience, converting these viewers into subscribers could be an area for strategic focus.

On the other hand, subscribed viewers, totalling 2,517 views, show a higher level of engagement with an average view duration of 44 seconds and 45.2% of each video watched, contributing to 31.1 hours of watch time.

Channel Statistics

(WATCH TIME BY AGE)

The Elene YouTube channel's viewership demographics reveal a diverse audience with varying levels of engagement across different age groups:

Viewers aged 65+ make up 17.8% of the total views, with the highest engagement levels, as evidenced by an average view duration of 1 minute and 11 seconds and a notable average percentage viewed at 73.5%. This age group contributes a significant 31.1% to the total watch time, suggesting that the content resonates well with this demographic.

Viewers between 55 and 64 years old account for 10.7% of the views, with the most prolonged engagement in terms of average view duration at 1 minute and 30 seconds and an impressive average percentage viewed at 85.2%. Their watch time adds up to 23.6%, indicating that this group finds the content particularly relevant and engaging.

The 25–34-year-old viewers represent a significant portion of the audience at 24.5%. However, their engagement is lower, with an average view duration of 33 seconds and 35.8% of the content viewed on average, contributing 20.1% to the total watch time. This suggests room for improved engagement strategies for this age bracket.

The 18–24-year-olds, the largest viewer age group, make up 27.1% of the views, but with the shortest average view duration of 29 seconds and an average percentage viewed at 28.2%. They contribute 19.7% to the total watch time. This indicates that while they are the biggest audience, their engagement is relatively shallow.

Channel Statistics

(WATCH TIME BY AGE)

Viewers aged 45–54 have a moderate share of views at 16.0% but exhibit the lowest engagement, with an average view duration of just 8 seconds and 8.3% of the content viewed, accounting for only 3.5% of the total watch time. This suggests that the content may not be as appealing or relevant to this demographic.

The 35–44-year-old viewers, although representing the smallest viewer segment at 4.0%, show a moderate level of engagement with an average view duration of 20 seconds and 40.1% of the content viewed, contributing 2.0% to the overall watch time. This indicates a selective but engaged viewership within this age range.

In summary, the Elene YouTube channel has a varied viewership with the most substantial engagement from older adults, who spend more time and view a larger portion of the videos. Young adults, while forming the largest group of viewers, tend to watch for shorter durations and less of each video. This analysis suggests potential areas for Elene to tailor content or outreach strategies to increase engagement across the younger demographics while continuing to cater to the highly engaged older audience.

Channel Statistics

(VIEWERS BY GENDER)

The Elene YouTube channel's audience composition and engagement metrics present an interesting divide across gender lines:

Female Viewers: Women account for 42.5% of the channel's views. They have an average view duration of 40 seconds and typically watch 41.0% of a video. This group contributes to 43.5% of the total watch time.

Male Viewers: Men make up a larger portion of the audience at 57.5% of the views. They have a slightly lower average view duration of 38 seconds and an average percentage viewed of 37.4%. Despite this, males account for a higher proportion of watch time at 56.6%.

Overall, while male viewers are more numerous on the Elene channel, female viewers show marginally higher engagement per video. This could provide valuable insights for content strategy, suggesting a potential to increase overall engagement by tailoring content to the viewing preferences of both genders or by creating content that encourages longer viewing sessions for male viewers.

Channel Statistics

(VIEWABILITY ACROSS DEVICES)

The device usage statistics for the Elene YouTube channel offer insights into the preferred methods of content consumption by the viewers:

Mobile Phones: Emerge as the dominant device for viewers, accounting for 58.9% of the total views, which amounts to 3,657 views. The watch time from mobile phones is also the highest at 41.2 hours, representing 59.1% of the total watch time. The average view duration on mobile phones is 40 seconds. This indicates that a significant majority of the audience prefers accessing the content on-the-go or finds it convenient to use their mobile devices for learning.

Computers: Represent the second most popular device with 2,307 views, making up 37.2% of total views. Computers account for 26.8 hours of watch time, which is 38.5% of the total. The average view duration on computers is slightly higher than mobiles at 41 seconds, suggesting that viewers using computers are slightly more inclined to watch for longer periods.

Tablets: Account for a small fraction of the views at 153, which is 2.5% of the total. The watch time on tablets is 0.9 hours, contributing to just 1.3% of the overall watch time, and the average view duration is 20 seconds. This much lower engagement might be due to less frequent use of tablets or a preference for other devices when engaging with YouTube content.

TV: Has the least number of views at 90, constituting 1.5% of the total, with a watch time of 0.8 hours, which is about 1.2% of the channel's total watch time. The average view duration for TV viewers is 33 seconds. While TV viewership is minimal, those who do watch via TV spend a relatively longer time per view compared to tablet users, possibly suggesting a more relaxed and potentially communal viewing experience.

Conclusion

Elene

@Project_elene · 123 subscribers · 81 videos

Project ELENE : This partnership is formed by organizations from Poland, Slovenia, Spain, ... >

eleneproject.eu and 3 more links

Subscribed

The Elene YouTube channel presents itself as an effective educational platform, particularly noteworthy for its appeal to older demographics. The analytics suggest a strong engagement from viewers aged 55 and above, who not only account for a significant portion of the watch time but also engage with the content more thoroughly than other age groups. This is indicative of the channel's content being well-suited to the interests and learning preferences of this demographic, perhaps due to the use of situational English and practical dialogues that resonate with their for tangible, real-world language applications.

Furthermore, the channel's method of teaching situational English through interactive dialogues appears to be a successful strategy, as evidenced by the substantial watch times and engagement levels. This approach caters well to adult learners who benefit from contextual learning scenarios that simulate real-life conversations.

In terms of content delivery, the data reveals a predominant preference for mobile devices, suggesting that the channel's audience values the flexibility to learn anywhere and at any time.

In conclusion, Elene's YouTube channel is adeptly positioned to serve as a valuable resource for older adults seeking to learn English through practical, situation-based content. With its mobile-optimized delivery and engaging format, the channel is well-equipped to meet the needs of lifelong learners in a digitally evolving educational landscape.

@Project_elene

Elene

@Project_elene · 123 subskrybentów · 81 filmów

Partnerstwo to tworzą organizacje z Polski, Słowenii, Hiszpanii, Portugalii i Turcji. Wśród te... >

eleneproject.eu i jeszcze 3 linki

Subskrybuj

Główna Video Shorts Playlists Społeczność

Elene app for learning English

100 wyświetleń · 2 miesiące temu

An application for learning English using the Situation Learning method, created as part of the "Elders learning English for Europe ERASMUS+" project no. 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465.

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/de...>

POKAŻ WIĘCEJ

Utworzone playlisty

<p>Project dissemination Wyświetl całą playlistę</p>	<p>App Wyświetl całą playlistę</p>	<p>Situation stories Wyświetl całą playlistę</p>	<p>Short films Wyświetl całą playlistę</p>	<p>Vocabulary Wyświetl całą playlistę</p>	<p>Questions & Answers Wyświetl całą playlistę</p>
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Popularne filmy ▶ Odtwórz wszystkie

<p>ASKING FOR DIRECTIONS Learn English with me Asking for directions ELEN... 259 wyświetleń · 4 miesiące temu</p>	<p>THE FIRST MEETING Learn English with me English Conversation... 241 wyświetleń · 4 miesiące temu</p>	<p>PRACTICAL VOCABULARY UNDERGROUND - ELENE 209 wyświetleń · 3 miesiące temu</p>	<p>ELENE CONVERSATION PRACTICE Useful expressions (The first conversation) - conversatio... 186 wyświetleń · 4 miesiące temu</p>	<p>PRACTICAL VOCABULARY AT A RESTAURANT Practical vocabulary At a restaurant - ELENE 142 wyświetlenia · 4 miesiące temu</p>	<p>VOCABULARY BOOKING A TOUR Practical vocabulary Booking a tour - ELENE 136 wyświetleń · 3 miesiące temu</p>
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